

Socio-Technical Perceptions of Hydrogen in the Energy Transition: Stakeholder Insights on Regional Impacts and Public Acceptance

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Abstract

Emerging alternative fuels, such as hydrogen, are spurring investments to scale up production and accelerate the transition to clean energy. As industries and governments explore large-scale deployment of hydrogen infrastructure, there is a need to critically examine stakeholder perceptions of the hydrogen supply chain. Additionally, pathways that enable the public to meaningfully engage in decision-making and ensure their opinions and concerns are adequately addressed can form the basis of trusted partnerships. To highlight this opportunity and existing issues, we conduct a qualitative analysis of interviews with 55 stakeholders in Texas, U.S., and assess their perceptions of hydrogen technologies and public engagement strategies. Our findings reveal significant gaps in stakeholders' understanding of economic and environmental concerns alongside limitations in proposed community education and engagement approaches, particularly among stakeholders in private energy companies. Addressing these knowledge and engagement gaps is critical to facilitating public participation and acceptance of this emerging infrastructure.

Keywords: Hydrogen, energy transition, stakeholders, public acceptance

1. Introduction

To achieve deep decarbonization and mitigate climate change impacts, the global energy sector needs a rapid energy transition away from fossil fuels and towards sustainable energy technologies. Most commonly, this includes aggressive deployment of renewable energy technologies like wind and solar, which can be used in conjunction with end-use electrification to decarbonize a variety of end-use sectors. However, as these technologies continue to expand, it is critical to understand public perceptions, especially as public buy-in is critical for accelerated adoption, and for avoiding historical patterns of exclusion in decision-making and the distribution of benefits – key hallmarks of a just energy transition [1]. Individual intentions to accept or reject an energy technology are known to be largely governed by perceived risks and benefits, which in turn are influenced by the

individual's levels of trust [2], [3], [4]. Particularly with emerging technologies, the perceived usefulness and ease of use of a technology also play prominent roles [5].

A range of emerging technologies and fuels have gained notoriety for their potential to decarbonize end-uses when direct electrification and the use of renewable energy are not feasible. Hydrogen, in particular, is an alternative energy carrier that can be produced through a carbon-free process (e.g., using renewable electricity) and can be used to decarbonize transportation and industrial processes. As with other technologies, the potential adoption of hydrogen requires an understanding of public perceptions and sentiment surrounding it and its potential impact. Social acceptance of technologies has previously been conceptualized into three primary components: *(i)* Market acceptance, *(ii)* Socio-political acceptance, and *(iii)* Community acceptance [6]. The recent interest in deploying hydrogen-based technologies in the U.S. reflects increased market acceptance from investors [7], [8]. However, the state of socio-political (e.g., acceptance by stakeholders and the public generally) and community acceptance (e.g., trust and acceptance by local stakeholders) requires further research, especially in regions where these technologies are expected to be adopted.

Current literature on public perception and acceptance of hydrogen infrastructure identifies key factors for community acceptance, including prior knowledge of hydrogen, perceived benefits and risks, institutional trust, and environmental knowledge [9], [10], [11]. Meanwhile, studies examining acceptance of end-use hydrogen technologies identify financial impacts, lack of information, and social factors as key drivers of acceptance and highlights the need to identify pathways for educating the public on this new technology [12]. Helping the public to better understand the potential costs and benefits of these technologies is necessary to ensure both that the public is well-informed and that their concerns about new infrastructure are being met. However, more work is needed to identify best practices for public engagement and education, as existing communications and media tend to focus on aspects of the hydrogen supply chain that are of little interest to the public [13], [14].

Additionally, more regional and local assessments of hydrogen acceptance are needed to understand regional differences in perceptions and identify localized barriers to acceptance [15]. Regional studies of the perceptions and impacts of technologies can help to refine theoretical frameworks of social acceptance by identifying specific economic, environmental, or other perceived risk factors [16], [17] as well as identifying barriers and pathways to engaging and communicating with the general public [18]. Similarly, such studies can then also provide insights into local acceptance of new infrastructure, as there is evidence that, even in cases where theoretical acceptance of hydrogen is high, there is a significant gap between that and a willingness for hydrogen infrastructure to be sited locally [19], [20].

As the hydrogen supply chain develops, there is a persistent need to communicate and engage with the public to ensure they are both active and informed participants in this energy transition [21], [22]. Despite this need, evidence suggests that populations often feel excluded from the decision-making processes for new energy infrastructure and are rarely engaged with directly [23]. And, in the absence of effective pathways for public participation, there is little evidence that stakeholders themselves have an understanding of local perceptions and impacts of new technologies. Even though hydrogen and energy stakeholder perspectives highlight public engagement as a key priority, their perceptions of public needs or concerns related to new hydrogen technologies rarely align with actual public perceptions, particularly in rural communities [24], [25]. Given this persistent gap, there is a growing need to explicitly include local, regional, and national-level impacts in decision-making and to encourage public participation in these topics [26], [27].

The lack of effective community engagement and stakeholder knowledge of public concerns about hydrogen technologies risks exacerbating existing inequities in our energy systems. In particular, it contributes to procedural inequities where communities are excluded from the decision-making process, resulting in a primarily top-down planning system that fails to account for local perspectives and concerns [28]. It also limits our ability to identify and recognize ongoing social, economic, and environmental issues in communities and how installation of new hydrogen infrastructure may exacerbate these issues [29]. Addressing these procedural and recognitional inequities are critical for ensuring the costs and benefits of the energy system and emerging technologies are equitably distributed [1], [30], [31], [32]. Achieving this requires the general public to be an active participant in the decision-making process or, in the absence of improved participatory frameworks, for stakeholders to be aware of and willing to address local concerns related to the energy transition. In light of this, there is a persistent need to understand who will be affected by the deployment of new hydrogen technologies, how they will be affected, and how to best communicate and engage with them to ensure their concerns are understood and addressed.

To better understand perceptions of hydrogen technologies and the energy transition, we conduct a series of 55 fully structured interviews with stakeholders in the energy sector in Texas. Through these interviews, we aim to understand the current issues faced by the communities or regions these stakeholders are active in, how the energy transition and potential adoption of hydrogen technologies may affect their communities, and existing public knowledge on these technologies and their impacts. Moreover, we seek to help bridge the gap between current stakeholders and the general public and identify gaps in their perceptions of emerging hydrogen technologies. By engaging with stakeholders from industry, electric utilities, local governments, and other organizations throughout the state, we develop insights into a region that is likely going to be a key player in the development of the hydrogen supply chain in the US and capture the range of different perspectives and issues that can help stakeholders in and outside the region. With this in mind, we address the following research questions:

1. To what extent are stakeholders able to identify issues present in communities and how might those issues impact perceptions of emerging technologies?
2. What are stakeholder perceptions of the energy transition and the potential role of hydrogen in their community? How well do stakeholder perceptions of public acceptance align with the public’s true perceptions?
3. What pathways are available to both educate and engage community members to facilitate public participation and acceptance of new technologies?
4. How do these pathways and perceptions vary across different stakeholders and regions?

Based on the findings of these interviews, we identify key issues and how stakeholders believe they may be mitigated or exacerbated by hydrogen supply chain development. Additionally, we identify gaps in both stakeholder perceptions of their communities and in current communication and education strategies that need to be addressed to ensure the public is both an informed and active participant in the decision-making process for prospective hydrogen projects.

2. Methods

2.1 Data Collection

We conducted fully structured interviews with 55 participants from 38 different communities in Texas (Supplemental Figure S1). Initial recruitment efforts utilized purposive sampling in order to identify individuals with significant connections to the community they live in and could speak to existing concerns in the area [33]. Our study prioritized organizations working in energy and environmental justice and then expanded using convenience sampling [34] to include individuals living in the community with a background in the energy sector. As a result, a variety of different stakeholder groups are represented in this sample, as shown in Table 1 along with other relevant information. The majority of participants are from electric utilities or other energy companies, with smaller fractions coming from local government, community organizations, or academia. Participants have a roughly even mix of technical and non-technical occupations and backgrounds, and come from a diverse mix of smaller rural communities as well as larger population centers. Interviews were conducted individually by a group of researchers from June 1, 2024, to August 16, 2024. All interviews were conducted in person in English, lasting 20-60 minutes, and recorded with permission from the participants.

Table 1: Summary statistics of participants in this study.

Participant Information	Number of Participants	Percentage
<i>Total</i>	55	100%
<i>Job Sector</i>		
Industry	27	49%

Government	8	15%
Utilities	7	13%
Community/NGO	5	9%
Academia	3	5%
Other	5	9%
<i>Job Type</i>		
Technical	25	45%
Non-technical	30	55%
<i>Community Size</i>		
10,000 – 100,000	19	34%
100,000 – 1,000,000	30	55%
> 1,000,000	6	11%

The interview protocol was designed to capture both the participant’s experiences within their community as well as their perceptions of current and future issues with the community. We asked questions regarding (1) their personal history, current work, and role in the community, (2) their perceptions of existing issues in the community, (3) community and personal perceptions of hydrogen and renewable energy technologies, (4) potential benefits and harms to the community caused by these technologies, and (5) communication and education strategies to engage with and inform the community about these technologies. The protocol was reviewed by the Institutions Review Board prior to data collection (IRB ID 2019090068-MOD05). The questions in the interview protocol were developed by two researchers and reviewed by multiple subject matter experts in hydrogen and clean energy technologies to ensure all relevant topics are addressed and to mitigate potential biases. The complete protocol is available in the Supplementary Materials.

2.2 Qualitative Analysis

Transcription and quality assurance and control of all interviews was performed using Otter.ai [35] and all coding was done in Dedoose [36], a qualitative coding software. For this analysis, we used a hybrid inductive-deductive coding method. First, analysis is split into two primary themes: “Current Regional Conditions”, which reflects the current state of the community or region where the participant lives and works, and “Energy Transition Impacts”, which captures both perceived and desired potential impacts of new energy technologies by the participant. Within each of these categories, we define five main dimensions, as described in Table 2. These categories are identified based on existing studies that apply qualitative methods to study the impacts and perceptions of hydrogen and adequately encapsulate themes and topics found in prior literature [11], [37], [38]. Within each of these themes, we allow for emergent inductive codes to capture specific ideas topics covered within the dataset (Figure 1). Multiple codes can be applied to each excerpt, which we define as a complete response to a single question and can exist anywhere from a short sentence to a paragraph in length. For example, the excerpt “As long as it provides jobs and lowers the monthly bill to our community, I’m open to it” was coded for both *Workforce Opportunities* and *Lower Energy Costs*. This method ensures that our findings can be compared with existing

literature using well-defined aspects of the energy transition while still allowing for new ideas and themes to emerge from the data [39]. The complete dictionary that includes all the emergent codes developed in this study is available in the Supplementary Materials. The inductive codes were created by three researchers and validated with two intercoder reliability assessments that occurred halfway through and at the conclusion of the coding process. A kappa coefficient was calculated between each pair of researchers performing the reliability assessment and the average coefficient was used to assess the overall quality of the dictionary. The resulting kappa coefficient ($\kappa=0.80$) indicates a satisfactory level of agreement between all three researchers [40].

Table 2: Description of the five main dimensions discussed and identified in this study.

Dimension	Description	Examples
Economic	Related to the economic and market conditions of a community or region.	<p>“Biggest economic issues facing our community would be unemployment and not enough pay.”</p> <p>“Well, my immediate thought would be: how much is it going to cost to get the hydrogen if I want to buy it from you?”</p>
Environmental	Related to natural systems, climate conditions and impacts in a region.	<p>“I mean, we're in the middle of the desert, so access to water is, and it has been for a long time, a top concern.”</p> <p>“The first would be emissions from power plants, coal fired power plants, um, less natural gas fired power plants, but all of those have very localized air quality impacts”</p>
Infrastructure & Technology	Related to the construction, operation, and management of new or existing energy infrastructure.	<p>“...we have these businesses coming in and they're wanting much more 100 megawatts, you know, just an astronomical amount of energy use than what we used to see.”</p> <p>“...there's a lot of a lot of difficulties with hydrogen. Things like transmission and storage and different things like that.”</p>
Governance & Policy	Related to the decisions and impacts of local, state, or federal governments and their policy decisions	<p>“Our government, um, you know, we are heavily regulated. I call it the convergence of arrogance and ignorance. And you got the government that knows enough to be dangerous about our business. And they're passing policies that they don't understand the impacts.”</p>

Social & Community	Related to community culture and perceptions of technologies	<p>“It’s probably gonna be like most other [places], they’re probably going to take the NIMBY approach, not in my backyard.”</p> <p>“I wouldn’t think the regular citizen would be very familiar with what hydrogen is.”</p>
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Figure 1: Example of the hierarchical coding structure used in this analysis. Parent codes are defined based on common themes identified in existing literature on hydrogen and technology adoption, and child codes are defined during the coding process to capture emergent themes.

3. Results

The thematic coding analysis characterized stakeholder perceptions of the current state of communities in Texas, their perspectives on the energy transition, and pathways to improve public engagement during the transition. Here, we present the most common findings within each of these areas before identifying gaps in stakeholder perceptions and further discussion of how these findings fit into the broader goal of achieving a just transition. The complete frequency tables showing participant response rates and the total number of occurrences for each code are available in the Supplemental Materials.

3.1 Theme 1: Current Regional Conditions

3.1.1 Presence of Energy Companies and Services

The results of the coding analysis suggest that energy companies have a significant economic presence in 64% of the communities in this study. While the majority of respondents associated the economic benefits of the energy sector with existing oil and gas infrastructure, 32% indicate that renewable energy capacity in some way benefit their community economically, typically either by providing jobs or lowering energy costs. Nearly all participants indicated that they have energy infrastructure operating in or near their community (e.g., oil and gas extraction, electricity generation), with 64% of participants describing nearby oil and gas facilities, and 73% discussing nearby renewable generation like wind and solar facilities. Notably, only 8 participants indicated that their community has hydrogen projects in production or being developed. Most of those participants are from communities along the Gulf Coast that either have existing hydrogen infrastructure for industrial demand or expect to be served by one of the new Hydrogen Hubs being developed as pilot projects across the country [41].

Furthermore, 21% of respondents indicate that energy companies have a growing presence in their communities, which can include new employment opportunities, new infrastructure, or other investments. Alongside this growth, 14% of participants specifically express concerns about ongoing demand growth, with an additional 29% discussing current projections for future load growth (e.g., from data centers, electrification, and other new technologies) and how that will impact the power grid. Given these concerns, 37% of participants describe how their current electricity system's infrastructure is insufficient, often citing old or outdated generation capacity and a need for more significant transmission and distribution line capacity. In the case of hydrogen, most participants who discussed this issue noted the need for new pipeline systems and other end-use infrastructure to properly transport and use hydrogen.

3.1.2 Concerns about Affordability and Employment

When discussing economic issues faced by their community, participants largely emphasize concerns about affordability and employment. Half of all respondents indicate that energy costs are a major concern for people in their community. While these concerns are driven, in part, by high rates of poverty in some communities, many participants describe an ongoing increase in electricity rates that they fear will strain residential customers. Multiple participants observed an ongoing rise in electricity rates, with one stating that “the price of energy keeps going up, so it's a big challenge for everybody” and another saying “[Electricity prices have] been steadily growing, growing, and it really hasn't hit a plateau”. Rising rates are also part of a broader concern about the increase in the cost of living, which was discussed by 30.3% of participants without any additional prompting.

Rising costs of living and energy affordability issues are also accompanied by concerns about employment opportunities within communities. Roughly a quarter of participants are concerned about job security, as members of their community are experiencing lay-offs and unemployment due to an uncertain labor market. Moreover, there are concerns about the overall quality of the jobs available in many regions. While definitions of job quality varied across respondents, adequate pay was a recurring theme across the 18 participants that mentioned the topic. When describing the state of their local economy, one participant said, “a lot of people are jobless right now... it’s hard for them to find a job that can actually pay well right now for them to pay the bills”. This suggests that, while a majority of participants claim their community has a relatively healthy job market, employment remains a persistent problem for many communities and, when paired with concerns about energy affordability and rising costs of living, reveal a need for new investments in these communities to offset growing economic uncertainty.

Notably, these concerns are not uniformly distributed across participants, as industry participants tend to be far more optimistic about current economic conditions. Compared to other participants, individuals working for energy companies are more likely to express no concerns about energy affordability (18% vs. 33%), less likely to perceive issues related to job security (22% vs. 32%), and more likely to describe their local economy positively (66% vs 44%). Although this could be, in part, driven by regional differences, this discrepancy is present even when you only compare their responses to other participants from the same area. Based on this, industry stakeholders appear to be relatively insulated from local economic conditions and that they may not be able to adequately identify such issues if and when they arise.

3.1.3 Environmental Impacts and Resilience

In terms of environmental concerns, the majority of participants are broadly concerned about emissions concerns and the potential impacts of climate change (55%). These issues commonly overlap with discussions about poor air quality in communities, which are mentioned by roughly half of all participants. Concerns about air quality tend to be either caused by tailpipe emissions from vehicles (“The biggest source of those pollutants is actually vehicles”), existing fossil fuel activity (“...the pollution that they face from the myriad of chemical and chemical facilities and refineries...”), or other industrial processes in their community (“there's a lot of big industries that just contaminate the air”). Additionally, roughly half of all participants discuss issues related to water in their community. Eighteen (33%) participants, particularly those in areas prone to drought, indicate that access to water is a persistent problem and is “always on the community’s mind”. Additionally, 19 participants describe concerns about the impacts of industry on water quality and pollution. Such concerns vary widely in severity, with some participants simply disliking the taste of the water from their tap, and others complain of recurring issues with chemical and bacteria present in their water systems. Environmental concerns were not evenly distributed

across all participants, with participants from energy companies much less likely to express concerns about air quality (41% vs. 57%) and water pollution (22% vs. 46%).

The majority of participants (32) expressed concerns about extreme weather and its impacts on their infrastructure and community members. Types of extreme weather varied depending on the region the respondent lived in, ranging from droughts to hurricanes, but 62% specifically mentioned Winter Storm Uri, an extreme weather event that caused widespread blackouts and significant damage across the state in 2021 [42]. While this event occurred over five years ago, the severity of the event and the resulting outages have significantly impacted participant and public perceptions of the power sector, with one participant saying the storm “really scared a lot of people and reduced confidence in our power providers” and another describing it as a “crisis of confidence with electrical reliability”. Participants involved with electric utilities also describe how winter storms and more extreme weather place strain on their local systems, as they now need to be prepared to manage extreme peaks in both the winter and the summer. These concerns, however, are not shared by most industry participants, as only 37% expressed concerns about extreme weather compared to 78% of all non-industry participants. As part of this discussion, nearly two-thirds of participants expressed concerns about energy reliability and resilience in their community, frequently citing Winter Storm Uri as an example of their power system failing. Along with the impacts of extreme weather, participants often expressed concerns about the reliability of renewable energy systems and how that may impact their power system in both typical and extreme operating conditions.

3.1.4 Impacts of Governance and Political Barriers

Aspects of governance and policy were a relatively small portion of the themes discussed in this study, with only 6% of total code occurrences. When discussed, the focus is most commonly on state and federal policy impacts on their community and the energy sector. Participants regularly discussed the economic benefits of the tax credits implemented under the Inflation Reduction Act as well as the environmental standards put into place by various regulatory bodies. Roughly a third of participants also describe political barriers that may be relevant to the deployment of hydrogen and renewable energy systems, including the politicization of clean energy technologies at the state and local level, often resulting in a gridlock that prevent forward progress (“energy has been polarized, politicized, and unfortunately, not for the benefit of anyone. And there are a lot of stakeholders [and] it's difficult to meet all of those stakeholders in a common place”). For many of the smaller communities included in this study, there were significant concerns about funding availability to support infrastructure development. Often, the funding available to these communities is insufficient for larger projects and can only be used to address more pressing concerns. As described by one participant, “there's only so much money to go around, and usually you're bandaid-ing or just fixing a piece of the problem versus all of the problem”. In many cases, energy companies operating in a community are bringing in labor from outside the community,

thereby limiting the economic benefits and providing fewer funds that could go toward public services. Additionally, 11% of respondents believe that a lack of relevant knowledge from decision-makers, primarily local government officials, will continue to cause problems and halt development. Participants suggest that this lack of knowledge will limit their ability to make beneficial decisions for their community, saying that officials lack “a true understanding of what the city really needs, they're way behind [on] infrastructure”.

3.2 Theme 2: Participant perceptions of the energy transition

3.2.1 Participant Familiarity with Hydrogen

In addition to current community conditions, we discuss the potential impacts of the energy transition with participants to understand their personal perceptions and how they think emerging technologies will impact their community. Figure 2 shows the summary of participants’ self-reported knowledge on different aspects of the hydrogen supply chain on a scale from one to ten. Average ratings are 5.3, 5.42, 5.16, and 5.40 for general hydrogen knowledge, hydrogen production methods, hydrogen infrastructure requirements, and hydrogen applications. Reported familiarity with hydrogen is higher amongst participants with a technical occupation (5.92) compared to individuals with non-technical backgrounds (4.8). This is also true when asked about the infrastructure requirements for hydrogen (5.65 vs. 4.75), but the difference is negligible when asked about more broadly about different hydrogen production methods (5.43 vs. 5.41) and hydrogen applications (5.47 vs. 5.36). This suggests that information about specific aspects of the hydrogen supply chain, primarily production methods and end-uses, have been able to reach non-technical stakeholders, but their overall knowledge on this new sector is limited. However, the rating distribution is relatively consistent across different occupations, suggesting that there is no correlation amongst this set of participants’ occupations and their perceived knowledge of the hydrogen supply chain.

Figure 2: Ratings of stakeholder’s perceived knowledge about different hydrogen topics from zero to ten.

In addition to comparatively high knowledge ratings for hydrogen end-uses, 75% of all participants made reference to specific end-uses for hydrogen and how they may or may not benefit their community. Of these participants, the majority discuss the use of hydrogen as a fuel for both light-duty (i.e., passenger cars) and heavy-duty transportation and freight (i.e., large trucks, freight, planes). Participants discuss how hydrogen fuel cell vehicles could reduce vehicle emissions while still maintaining short refueling times, often comparing them to electric vehicles and their charging infrastructure. This comparison is also extended to concerns about infrastructure availability, as participants are uncertain about the ability to effectively build out transportation demand for hydrogen given the absence of refueling infrastructure for hydrogen, stating:

“...there's no infrastructure where people can fill up for hydrogen. So, what happens to that getting traction within the community? It doesn't work, right? If you can't fill up your car, you can't go anywhere.”

This leads to a dilemma identified by multiple participants, where you need to have infrastructure in place in order to develop end-use demand for hydrogen, but stakeholders are unlikely to invest in infrastructure without the promise of some demand for hydrogen (“you have to have the level of demand to make a business justifiable, right? An investor is not going to invest that amount of money if there's no potential profit”). Other hydrogen end-uses identified by stakeholders, such as industrial processes or residential heating, were less frequently discussed but are also less likely to experience significant infrastructure barriers due to existing gas infrastructure. However, due to the many barriers associated to implementation and potentially limited uses, several participants

are not convinced that hydrogen makes sense for their community (“I’m not sure we have any power, focus, and use for hydrogen, besides just reducing emissions.”).

The other major end-use identified by end-users is the use of hydrogen to support the power sector. Stakeholders identify two ways for hydrogen to be used for power generation. The first is to use hydrogen in combustion turbines, often mixed with natural gas as a way to reduce emissions from thermal generation. The other, more commonly discussed, method is to leverage hydrogen as a storage asset by using excess electricity from wind and solar resource which can then be either sold and exported or converted back to electricity locally (“we are creating demand in this community, which helps us to effectively use our resources from wind and solar within this community, rather than exporting it”). This suggests that stakeholders view hydrogen as a way to assuage existing concerns about grid reliability, specifically related to renewable energy, and as a potentially alternative revenue stream for communities that may not have an immediate need for hydrogen themselves.

3.2.2 Perceptions of Local Hydrogen Siting

Additionally, 36% of participants described specific hydrogen production methods they would like to see in their community. Despite steam methane reformation (SMR) being a much more mature method for hydrogen production, many participants are concerned about the potential emission impacts of SMR facilities and are thus more drawn to electrolyzers for their reduced environmental impacts. However, other participants are quick to note the non-emission impacts associated with electrolyzers, notably the large land requirement for new renewable energy capacity to power those facilities as well as the water consumption. In particular, many participants from drought-prone regions are not convinced that electrolyzers would be viable in their community, despite their high renewable energy potential, as stated by a participant, “it’s probably not very optimal to be using a lot of the water that we barely have for our community in a project like that”.

Concerns about hydrogen facilities frequently focused on safety and siting, as a majority of participants discussed some level of concern about the safety of hydrogen technologies operating in or near their community (59%). In particular, the properties of hydrogen gas make it much more prone to leakages and potentially explosions, thus leading to frequent discussion about the need for tight regulations and safety measures for the production and transport of hydrogen. These concerns, along with less extreme impacts of having a facility nearby (e.g., noise, smell, visually unappealing, etc.) led to stakeholders frequently indicated that they and members of their community would likely not be willing to have these facilities sited near their homes, even if they indicated that they were more broadly accepting of the technology. This “not-in-my-backyard” philosophy was a common discussion point across the interviews (27%) and is likely going to significantly interfere with where and how these new technologies will be sited.

As new hydrogen infrastructure is deployed, several stakeholders, primarily those from community organizations, observe it will most likely be built in (1) areas that already have existing oil and gas infrastructure to support and (2) areas that have little political capital to protest or resist its installation. The first location type has fewer infrastructure barriers to building new hydrogen production facilities and will make it easier to develop the hydrogen supply chain in its early phases. Moreover, communities with existing fossil fuel infrastructure, particularly along the Gulf Coast, are also more likely to have a workforce with relevant skills and may already have an existing demand for hydrogen. However, communities that fall into the latter category will be forced to deal with potential negative ramifications of hydrogen projects with few means to resist. Moreover, stakeholders acknowledge that these same communities are often currently being negatively impacted by the presence of fossil fuel or other extractive industries, which make it even more difficult to derive benefits from new infrastructure:

“I wouldn't want to live next to one, and so what's going to happen is they're probably going to be located next to people who have very little political authority...and not a lot of economic choices about where they move because they don't want to be next to one...That also makes their promises of a very different future harder to achieve, because they're building them in communities where they've already created plight.”

In contrast to members of community organizations, participants from industry tend to be much more optimistic about the local siting of hydrogen infrastructure. Industry participants are both more likely to express little to no concerns about hydrogen technologies and expect the general public will be more receptive to local siting of hydrogen facilities. Only 18% of industry participants indicated that the public would react negatively to local hydrogen siting, compared to 25% of non-industry participants. Similarly, 63% of industry participants said that people would react positively to local hydrogen siting, compared to 46% of non-industry participants. While this may be, in part, a reflection of the different communities and regions that these participants are active in, it is also an indication that participants from industry do not have a full understanding of public perceptions of hydrogen and concerns about their impacts.

3.2.3 Expected risks and benefits from hydrogen adoption

Economic concerns about emerging hydrogen technologies focus primarily on (1) their ability to provide high-quality jobs and (2) their ability to provide affordable energy. The majority of participants discuss how they would hope that new hydrogen infrastructure would provide good, high-quality jobs for people in their community. Amongst these communities, there are significant differences in perceptions of their available workforce. Sixteen percent (16%) of participants described their current workforce as sufficiently skilled to work in emerging energy sectors, while another 16% emphasize the need for additional training and other resources to address current gaps

in experience and skills for their current workforce. The former sentiment is much more common in areas that already have significant energy infrastructure or other resources, such as one participant that stated “we have a pipeline to have a skilled workforce that can move away from fossil fuels and towards clean energy”. While participants are generally optimistic about the number of jobs hydrogen and renewables can create, some are uncertain about the quality of these emerging jobs, stating that they “don't seem to be able to generate the type of salaries for employees that the oil and gas world does”.

When asked how they would want hydrogen and renewable energy to benefit their community, 25% of participants discussed how they hope hydrogen would become an affordable energy alternative that would bring down rising costs. However, almost half of participants (44%) believed that hydrogen could be prohibitively expensive and unable to provide significant support to their community, suggesting uncertainty in long-term economic impacts. About a third of participants are optimistic about hydrogen’s ability to reduce carbon emissions and the presence of other pollutants in the air and water. These benefits are almost exclusively brought up when discussing electrolytic hydrogen specifically. While these benefits are discussed amongst stakeholders in this study, some participants are skeptical and think there are more effective approaches to reducing emissions (“...if we want to reduce environmental impact...I don't think hydrogen is the way to go forward”). Multiple participants also describe the risk of hydrogen leakage, especially when transported via pipeline, and how they could have an overall greater warming effect. While these sentiments are common amongst interviewees, participants believe that these environmental impacts will not be a primary motivator for people in their community. As one participant states, “I think that 25% will be thrilled that the environmental impact would be reduced, and the other 75 honestly probably wouldn't care too much”.

3.2.4 Different outcomes and expectations across community types

Perceptions of the energy transition and community characteristics vary considerably depending on whether or not a participant’s community has existing oil and gas infrastructure. Despite environmental impacts being more likely to be concentrated in oil and gas communities, participants from those areas are equally likely as their counterparts to be concerned about the environmental impacts of the power sector, including concerns about air quality and carbon emissions. This may also be reflective of the fact that many of the participants from these communities are from energy companies, which we previously determined were much less likely to raise specific environmental concerns. Participants are more likely to associate oil and gas infrastructure with positive economic impacts in their community, including employment and other investments. But they are also more concerned about future energy costs and are more likely to describe how energy costs could be lowered by new technologies and fuels like hydrogen. Similarly, they are more concerned about the potential job losses from the energy transition, but

the majority of participants from oil and gas communities also highlight the possibility of new workforce opportunities from hydrogen.

Beyond energy infrastructure, perceptions of the energy transition vary depending on the current issues present in a community. Participants who identify persistent issues in their community are more likely to be receptive to hydrogen technologies if they can address, or at the very least, not exacerbate, those problems. For instance, participants that describe environmental issues in their community, such as air quality concerns and water availability concerns, are more likely to express concerns about how hydrogen may exacerbate these issues relative to other participants (39% vs. 27% for air concerns and 44% vs 11% for water concerns). These stakeholders are also more likely to describe a lack of institutional trust amongst members of their community (44% vs. 30%) and indicate that the public is less informed about energy issues compared to other participants in this study (30% vs. 14%). Similarly, participants that describe economic issues in their community, namely energy affordability and job insecurity, are much more likely to express interest in hydrogen's ability to lower energy costs or provide employment opportunities (73% vs. 52%). This suggests that stakeholders in these communities are both cognizant of environmental issues currently present and are accounting for those issues when considering new infrastructure investments.

Community size can significantly impact energy transition perceptions. Participants from smaller (10k-100k), often rural (as defined by the US Department of Agriculture [43]), communities are less likely to describe environmental impacts than participants from more densely populated regions. Additionally, a lack of general energy knowledge is persistent across smaller communities, as they are most frequently described as lacking knowledge related to the energy sector (26%) and hydrogen (95%). Participants from these communities tend to also have the lowest understanding of hydrogen amongst stakeholders; they are less often able to identify hydrogen production methods and end-uses and, on average, rated their knowledge of these technologies 2-3 points lower than other participants. Some stakeholders also suggest that smaller, rural communities tend to have a more negative perception of renewable energy and their reliability, stating "all they care about is reliability and cost...they understand that wind and solar don't show up when you need 'em most, so they're not really gung-ho on it".

Regional differences can also be found amongst participants from different parts of the state. Participants from communities along the Gulf Coast, which tend to have large amounts of fossil fuel and industrial infrastructure (62%), are the least likely to express concerns about future energy prices (38%) and the most likely to describe the energy sector as a major employer in their community (75%). Despite this, they are also the most likely to express concerns about a lack of quality, high-paying jobs (63%). Participants from this region are also the most likely to discuss concerns about carbon emissions (87%), but are significantly less likely to talk about other environmental impacts relative to other participants. In contrast, stakeholders from the Permian

Basin – a region in west Texas where there are both large amount of oil and gas extraction and large amounts of renewable energy potential – express much greater concerns about the environmental impacts of fossil fuels (66%). Additionally, these stakeholders are much more likely to discuss the potential benefits of new hydrogen infrastructure and to think their community will react positively to its installation in their community (83%).

3.3 Community Education and Communication

In general, the vast majority (85.7%) of participants believe that members of their community or region have little to no knowledge of hydrogen as an energy source. Despite this lack of awareness, a majority of participant suggest that their community would be willing to adopt end-use hydrogen (52%) and would likely be open to hydrogen facilities operating in their communities (54%). A smaller, but still substantial group (42%) indicates that many communities would be open to renewable energy either being introduced or expanding in their communities. This discrepancy could be, in part, driven by the ongoing politization of renewable and green energy, particularly in Texas, as evidenced by participant descriptions of state and local government (see section 3.1) and well as proposed state legislation intended to hinder renewable energy production [44], [45]. Others are less optimistic about community interest in the development process, arguing that communities in general are going to be indifferent to emerging hydrogen technologies until they are already implemented and ready-to-use (“Most people are not even really gonna care until [they] have a choice of ‘I can buy a hydrogen vehicle versus a gasoline engine’”).

Participants largely recognize that active community participation is critical both to ensure that community needs are being met, for example in the siting process for a new facility, as well as to make a community more receptive to this new infrastructure. However, this involvement cannot occur until communities have a greater understanding of hydrogen and the energy sector more broadly, which they largely lack. To fill this educational gap, the majority of participants (29) suggest media campaigns to educate and inform the public. Of these participants, 17 suggest the use of social media, but more traditional media (e.g., news, commercials, radio, newspapers, etc.) are also referenced. Alternatively, engaging with the community directly through either political events or through events organized by private companies was also commonly discussed. Lastly, 13 participants discuss opportunities to expand formal educational opportunities by updating science curricula at different levels of education and providing external opportunities to engage with the energy sector through internships, site visits and other outreach programs with schools.

However, the efficacy of these education strategies, especially ones where stakeholders are directly engaging with a community, will be limited by the lack of public trust in energy companies that operate in these communities. This institutional distrust was explicitly mentioned by about a third of participants, often describing energy companies and other stakeholders as “hard to trust” due to past behavior and subpar communication. In particular, the lack of transparency when

communicating with the public is a commonly discussed issue, with participants describing the need for upfront communication that accurately and accessibly conveys the potential impacts of new hydrogen infrastructure. Moreover, this information should be appropriately tailored to the issues currently present in the community and how they may be exacerbated or assuaged by a company's activities. Alongside this, responses to questions about public trust further emphasized the perspective that communities need to be considered a stakeholder and be involved in the decision-making process for these projects. Some participants indicated that the issues of public trust stem directly from the ethos and missions of companies that try to operate in their community. They suggest that, in order to establish the trust necessary to facilitate a just transition, stakeholders need to adapt to a community and ensure they share in the benefits of any new projects while also deprioritizing constant profit.

Suggested pathways to collect community feedback focus primarily on either conducting surveys to collect large amount of relevant data, or collecting in-depth responses and facilitating discussions through panels, town halls, and focus groups. However, participants observe gaps in these strategies, as they are dependent on the public being aware of and willing to take advantage of these opportunities, which they are often unwilling to do. Few participants identified strategies for closing these gaps, although one participant described needing to essentially bribe community members to attend such events, while another instead suggests trying to maximize the accessibility of such events in order to "meet them where they are".

4. Discussion

Generally speaking, participants are able to identify that may be relevant to the general public and are often consistent with those identified in existing literature. Safety and siting concerns, for example, are recurring issues across the majority of interviews and are a key research area for the hydrogen economy [46], [47], and one of the primary barriers to public acceptance of local hydrogen siting. Adequately addressing safety concerns and overcoming "not in my backyard" sentiments are necessary to ensure equitable siting of this new infrastructure. Participants, particularly those from community organizations, expressed concerns that these sentiments can shift the siting of new hydrogen infrastructure into areas with little political power, which has also occurred historically with fossil fuel infrastructure [48], [49]. Alongside safety, participants frequently identified economic concerns, particularly related to job opportunities and energy costs, as issues within their community, which is also commonly referenced as a perceived concern in studies of public and social acceptance of hydrogen [47]. Additionally, stakeholders often recognize potential environmental impacts of hydrogen, but do not necessarily expect the public to share those concerns. One exception to this seems to be communities in drought-prone areas, where reliable access to water is a significant and ongoing concern and would likely result in significant public resistance to hydrogen electrolyzers.

The regional differences identified in this study emphasize the need to prioritize different information and strategies when engaging with and developing projects in different regions. Given the economic influence of oil and gas infrastructure in some communities, stakeholders from oil and gas communities tend to prioritize the economic impacts of new technologies and potential decline from a phase out of fossil fuels, which suggests that addressing these sentiments may be critical for driving hydrogen adoption. However, this trend is not consistent across all oil and gas communities, as participants from the Permian Basin are much more likely to emphasize the importance of the environment impacts of oil and gas extraction compared to those from the Gulf Coast. Rural communities also tend to have a unique set of challenges that can be significant barriers to implementation compared to urban communities. Participants from rural communities tend to have both the lowest knowledge and the most positive perceptions of hydrogen technologies. This, when combined with the relative lack of funding and infrastructure opportunities mentioned by many rural participants, suggests that rural communities may be particularly vulnerable to potential exploitation or otherwise poor investments in technologies not suited to their community. In general, these findings suggest that energy stakeholders have a general understanding of local contexts and public concerns when considering new infrastructure, but more detailed, localized assessments are needed in specific communities to more fully assess the gap between public concerns and stakeholder perceptions.

While stakeholders in this study overall have a general understanding of public concerns, there is a significant disconnect between industry stakeholders and other participants. While questions in the interview were framed in the context of an individual's community, responses from industry participants were consistently focused on technical issues that were removed from local contexts. As such, they were considerably less likely to describe current economic or environmental concerns relative to other participants and were more likely to describe their local economy positively. Industry stakeholders also overestimated positive public perceptions to local siting of hydrogen infrastructure relative to other participants, which suggests an insufficient understanding of the potential impacts of hydrogen infrastructure and how that relates to current conditions. Additional work is needed to ensure industry stakeholders in particular are well-aligned and able to account for public interests and concerns.

Gaps in stakeholder perceptions can potentially be remedied by robust community education strategies, but the methods described by participants in this study may not be sufficient. Participants generally agreed that community education and engagement are critical to infrastructure planning and siting, especially given the lack of public knowledge on hydrogen. However, participants identified major barriers to existing and proposed engagement strategies. For example, participants most commonly cited social media as a possible avenue to educate the public on hydrogen technologies. While it is potentially the most effective way to reach a large audience, social media is also an effective tool for spreading misinformation. In fact, when asked which sources of information they considered untrustworthy, the vast majority of participants

listed social media. In addition, efforts to engage with the public directly or through political institutions may allow for the distribution of more reliable information but could be hindered by low public trust and limited public participation in local politics. Despite participants often discussing the shortcomings of these strategies, few participants were able to identify or suggest changes to overcome them.

Furthermore, there is little evidence that current energy stakeholders are well equipped to engage with the public on issues related to hydrogen. Existing literature suggests that energy stakeholders tend to have limited knowledge of hydrogen [53] and many participants in this study expressed very limited understanding of different aspects of the hydrogen supply chain. Additionally, misinformation was also somewhat common in participant responses related to hydrogen, including those who described themselves as knowledgeable on the subject. For example, participants often incorrectly described how hydrogen was produced or how it could be used. Stakeholder perceptions of the hydrogen supply chain are also not always aligned with the realities of this emerging sector. Many of the end-uses discussed by stakeholders, such as light-duty transportation and residential heating, are unlikely to be competitive relative to other methods of decarbonization, such as direct electrification [51], [52]. Thus, further stakeholder education is needed to ensure they have a sufficient understanding of viable use cases for hydrogen, as well as its risks and benefits, before attempting to engage with the public on the subject.

These gaps in stakeholder knowledge, as well as their limited public engagement strategies, indicate that stakeholders are not prepared to support public participation in the planning of hydrogen infrastructure. Attempts to engage with the public with current proposed strategies would likely only reach a limited set of the general public and lead to misinformation about the potential impacts of hydrogen. Understanding the best way to engage with communities is critical and those connections and knowledge likely already exist within community and grassroots organizations. Fostering relationships between stakeholders and these existing community-based efforts can help build participatory frameworks for the public, ensure private stakeholders are adequately aware of local concerns, and help provide some means of accountability to the public should those concerns go unaddressed. Identifying and building robust participatory frameworks is critical for ensuring procedural justice and that the public has opportunities to participate in the planning process in a fair and accessible way.

The nature of qualitative research means there is a potential for research and cognitive biases both in data collection and in the analysis. Multiple steps have been taken to mitigate the impact of cognitive biases in both the data collection and analysis process. In data collection, we used a fully structured interview process where interviewers could not deviate from the provided protocol to ensure the same data is collected even when different interviewers are conducting the interviews. Quality assessment of the audio recordings and transcripts confirmed that all interviews followed the intended protocol. Similarly, two intercoder reliability checks were performed throughout the

qualitative coding process to clarify and refine the coding dictionary and minimize the potential bias from any of the individual researchers. Furthermore, we found that no new inductive codes emerged by the end of the coding process, implying that inductive thematic saturation was reached amongst this set of participants and all relevant information was extracted from the interview set [54]. Additionally, it should be noted that the participants in this interview were predominantly White and often associated with energy companies that may be operating in a community. While we seek to identify economic and environmental issues prevalent in communities and understand them from stakeholder perspectives, this analysis is not reflective of the disproportionate impacts of these issues on marginalized communities at the state and local level. Direct engagement with local communities and marginalized groups within those communities are critical to get firsthand accounts of they are impacted by an energy transition and to further elucidate the gap between their lived experiences and stakeholder understandings.

5. Conclusions

This study seeks to understand stakeholder perspectives on the energy transition and the potential impacts of emerging hydrogen technologies. Through an analysis of 55 interviews with stakeholders across 38 communities in Texas, we develop a clearer understanding of the current perceptions of hydrogen technologies and the energy transition, how those perceptions vary across different types of communities, and pathways for educating and engaging with the public moving forward. Stakeholder perceptions of new hydrogen technologies are generally positive, but levels of understanding of the technology and its potential impacts are inconsistent. While cost, workforce impacts, and safety are the predominant concerns across the state, participants from different regions and communities express different needs and concerns depending on both the size of their community as well as the existing presence of different energy infrastructure. In addition, stakeholders from energy companies are less frequently able to identify economic and environmental issues present in their community that could be impacted by new technology deployment compared to stakeholders in other occupations. Industry stakeholders also potentially overestimate the public's openness to hydrogen infrastructure being installed in their community, indicating major gaps in industry perceptions specifically. We determine that stakeholders can identify potential barriers to public adoption within their community, but gaps still persist in their ability to and understanding of how to engage with and educate the public. While this study attempts to engage with stakeholders from a variety of different communities in Texas, future work should emphasize understanding how to best leverage and build connections between stakeholders and the public within a single community. These granular, localized assessments are the only way to adequately ensure that the needs of individual communities would be effectively addressed by emerging technologies and to facilitate a more just transition.

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